

Relationship of the Kaniadakis Distribution to $d \ln(p)/dkx = \ln(p) r(kx)$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 30, 2026

In (1), the Kaniadakis distribution $p(kx)$ (where $x = -ei/T$) is studied as a solution of the differential equation $\sqrt{1+kx} dp/dx + p = 0$. Here we argue that $p(kx)$ is the solution such that dp/dkx returns $p(x) b(x)$. We further suggest that $p(kx) = \{g(kx) + kx\}$ power $1/k$ so that for $x \gg 1$, one has $p(kx) \rightarrow kx$ power $1/k$. For $x=0$, $g(kx)$ cannot be 0 as this is unphysical. The question becomes: How does one find $g(kx)$? We consider $dp/dx = p$ yielding the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution $p(x) = \exp(x)$ for $x = -ei/T$. If one wishes the above distribution $\{ \}$ power $1/k$ to become the Maxwell-Boltzmann for $x \rightarrow 0$, then it is actually the function within $\{ \}$ which should become $\exp(kx)$. This means that one should have a differential equation apply to the argument $\{ \}$ of $\{ \}$ power $1/k$, i.e. $d \ln(p)/dkx = \ln(p(kx)) r(kx)$ such that $r(kx) \rightarrow 1 + 0^*x$ in an $x \rightarrow 0$ expansion to create the MB distribution. This means that $dg/dkx + 1 = (g+kx) * r(kx)$. There are two ways in which this may occur. First, $dg/dkx = g/xk$ which means that $g=xk$ which implies $p(0)=0$ which is unphysical or $dg/dkx = xk/g$ which yields $g = \sqrt{1+kx}$ and $r=1/g$. This then satisfies the conditions above and leads to the Kaniadakis distribution: $p(kx) = \{\sqrt{1+kx} + kx\}$ power $1/k$.

Kaniadakis Distribution and Differential Equation

In (1), various mathematical properties of the Kaniadakis distribution (unnormalized):

$$p(kx) = \{ \sqrt{1+kx} + kx \} \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((1))$$

are studied. In particular, it is pointed out that ((1)) is a solution of the differential equation:

$$\sqrt{1+kx} dp/dx + p = 0 \quad ((2))$$

We note that this is of the form: $dp/dx = b(x) p(x)$ ((3)).

We also note that $dp/d(kx) = p(kx)$ leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution $\exp(-kx)$ for $k=1$ and $x = -ei/T$.

We suggest that in the finite k , but $x \rightarrow 0$ limit, the Kaniadakis distribution becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann. In the literature, one usually sets $k \rightarrow 0$, but the variable in question is kx and so one may leave k finite and set $x \rightarrow 0$ to obtain the MB distribution. The $1/k$ in ((1)) does not create the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, so it must arise from $\ln(p)$, i.e. the function in $\{ \}$ in ((1)). Thus, $\ln(p)$ itself and not only p should follow a differential equation of the form:

$$d/dkx \ln(p) = \ln(p(x)) r(x) \quad ((4))$$

We argue that the form ((4)) leads to a solution of the Kaniadakis distribution.

Obtaining the Kaniadakis Equation from $d/dkx \ln(p) = p(kx) r(kx)$

We suggest that applying a differential equation of the form ((3)) to $\ln(p)$, i.e. ((4)) leads to a particular math form which has the possibility of becoming the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution when $r(kx) \rightarrow 1$. This would suggest that in the $x \rightarrow 0$ limit, $r(x)$ has no first order in x term and that its leading constant is 1. This would then allow for p , to first order in x , be $\exp(-kx)$ so that the $1/k$ in $\{ \}$ power $1/k$ removes k .

We consider ways in which to create ((4)) with $r(x)$ having the required property mentioned above.

$$\text{If } \ln(p) = \{ g(kx) + kx \} \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{Then } d \ln(p)/dkx = \{ dg/dkx + 1 \} = p(kx) r(kx) \quad ((6))$$

We note that $\ln(p)$ has the form of ((5)) because for $x \gg 1$, one must have $p = (\text{number} * kx)$ power $1/k$. This implies restrictions on the form of $g(kx)$, but we will check these after finding a solution of ((6))

One wishes $dg/dkx + 1$ to be proportional to $p(kx)$ multiplied by a function of kx .

There are two ways to obtain this result. The first is

$$dg/dkx = g / (kx) \quad \text{or} \quad g = kx \quad ((7))$$

This cannot be correct because then $p(kx) = (\text{number} * kx)$ power $1/k$ which is 0 for $x=0$ which is unphysical.

$$\text{The second solution is: } dg/dkx = kx / g \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{This leads to } dg/dkx + 1 = 1/g (kx+g) = \ln(p) / g \quad ((9))$$

Thus, $g = r(kx)$, but one must find $g(kx)$ explicitly and see that in the $x \rightarrow 0$ limit it is 1 to first order in x (i.e. $0 * x$) and in the $x \gg 1$ limit $g(x) \rightarrow x$.

The form ((8)) is easily satisfied by considering $g = \sqrt{kkxx + 1}$ because the derivative of power $1/2$ yields power $-1/2$ and one needs $kkxx$ in the argument to obtain the kx on the RHS of ((8)). Thus:

$$g(kx) = \sqrt{1+kkxx}, \quad r(kx) = 1/g \quad \text{and} \quad p(kx) = \{ \sqrt{1+kkxx} + kx \} \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((10))$$

One may see that $r(kx)$ has a leading constant of 1 and 0^*x in an $x \rightarrow 0$ expansion and that $\ln(p) \rightarrow kx$ power $1/k$ for $x \gg 1$. Thus, the differential equation approach of ((4)) i.e. $d \ln(p) / dkx = \ln(p) r(kx)$ seems to work for deriving the Kaniadakis distribution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may consider a distribution of the form $p(kx) = \{ g(kx) + kx \}$ power $1/k$ such that for $kx \gg 1$, one has $p(kx) = (kx)$ power $1/k$. If $x=0$, $kx=0$, but $g(kx)$ is not 0, but is still unknown. We suggest that one may find $g(kx)$ explicitly in the following manner. In the case of $x \rightarrow 0$ for finite k , one may demand that $g(kx)+kx$ go as $\exp(kx)$ (where $x=-ei/T$). Now, $\exp(kx)$ satisfies $dp/dkx = p$ and so we suggest that $\ln(p) = g+kx$ should satisfy: $d \ln(p) / dkx = \ln(p) r(kx)$ such that $r(kx)$ has a leading 1 and 0^*x in a power law expansion for $x \rightarrow 0$, k finite. This means that $dg/dkx + 1 = (g+kx) * r(kx)$. There are two ways for the LHS to return $g+kx$. The first is that $dg/dkx = g/kx$ which means $g=kx$ which is unphysical because $p = (2kx)$ power $1/k$ which is 0 for $x=0$. The second way is for $dg/dkx = kx/g$ which yields $g=\sqrt{1+kx}$. Then for $x \gg 1$, $p = (2kx)$ power $1/k$ which is fine and $r(kx) = 1 + 0^*kx$ for $x \rightarrow 0$. Thus, we suggest that one may solve for the Kaniadakis distribution using the above differential equation approach.

References

1. Bolle, R. and Jarra, I. and Secret, J. An Exposition on the Kaniadakis k Deformed Decay Differential Equation (2025)

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